

Generalized Fractional Integral Forms of Newton-type Inequalities for Functions of Bounded Variation

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive framework for deriving Newton-type inequalities involving generalized fractional integrals for functions of bounded variation. By employing the concept of generalized fractional operators, several new integral inequalities are established, which extend and unify various existing results in the literature. Furthermore, by selecting specific forms of functions and appropriate parameter values, a number of significant special cases are obtained, demonstrating the wide applicability of the proposed approach. The results not only enhance the understanding of fractional inequalities but also provide a broader mathematical foundation for future research in fractional analysis and related areas.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities, generalized fractional integrals, functions of bounded variation.

1 Introduction

Over the past decades, several classical inequalities such as those of Hermite–Hadamard-type, Simpson-type, and Newton-type inequalities have attracted considerable attention. These type of inequalities have been generalized and extended by many researchers to accommodate different categories of functions, including convex, s -convex, quasi-convex, log-convex, and related classes. Such generalizations not only reveal deeper structural properties of mathematical inequalities but also expand their potential for applications in both pure and applied contexts.

In recent years, the development of fractional calculus has opened new perspectives in this field. Fractional integral and differential operators, due to their demonstrated applications in physics, engineering, and mathematical modelling, have provided powerful tools for extending classical inequalities. Numerous studies have explored Hermite–Hadamard-type, Simpson-type,

and Newton-type inequalities within the framework of fractional operators, leading to new bounds, refinements, and generalizations. Motivated by these developments, the study of Newton-type inequalities via generalized fractional integral operators has gained increasing importance. Such results not only unify existing inequalities but also produce novel extensions that are adaptable to wider classes of functions. This research area is expanding, adding valuable results to the literature and opening the way for further work and applications.

The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule forms the basis of Simpson's second rule. Computations involving three-step quadratic kernels are commonly referred to as Newton-type results, which are known in the literature as Newton-type inequalities. Many mathematicians have studied and extended these inequalities, exploring their properties and applications in various contexts. For example, in paper [1], some Newton-type inequalities are proved for the case of functions whose second derivatives are convex. Improvements are obtained, based on convexity, to some recent error estimates of Dragomir and Agarwal for the trapezoidal formula [2]. Corresponding estimates are also established for the midpoint formula, and a parallel development is presented based on concavity. Mihai et al. [3] establish new Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities for harmonic h -convex functions involving hypergeometric functions. They also discussed several new and known special cases that follow from these results. The methods and ideas presented in their work may inspire further research in this field. In paper [4], some Newton-type inequalities are acquired for the case of functions whose first derivative in absolute value at certain power are arithmetically-harmonically convex. In addition, in paper [5], some Newton-type inequalities are proved by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions and several Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities are presented for functions of bounded variation. Noor et al. [6] establish new Newton-type integral inequalities for p -harmonic convex functions. They also discuss several special cases as applications of these main results. Moreover, Ali et al. [7] consider some Newton-type inequalities for quantum differentiable convex functions. Erden [8] presents several error estimates for the Newton-type quadrature formula using bounded variation and Lipschitzian mappings. For recent results on Newton-type inequalities, see [10, 9] and the references therein.

Fractional calculus and its applications arise in various fields such as physics, chemistry, engineering, and mathematics. Extending classical analysis to fractional analysis provides more realistic solutions to many problems, since numerous real dynamical systems are more accurately modelled by non-integer order operators. While integer-order models in classical analysis often fail to represent natural processes, fractional computation with arbitrary and flexible orders yields more precise and reliable approaches. Motivated by its wide applicability, this area has been extensively investigated by many researchers. For example, in paper [11], inequalities involving fractional integrals have recently gained significant attention, leading to new developments in inequality theory. In this study, Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities are established using Atangana-Baleanu operators for twice differentiable convex functions, supported by a new integral identity. In [12], Hadamard inequalities for k -fractional Riemann-Liouville integrals are proved, and the classical fractional Riemann-Liouville case is deduced. These results are further extended to two coordinates, yielding Hadamard inequalities for fractional Riemann-Liouville integrals on two coordinates. In [13], a new definition of fractional derivative and fractional integral is

introduced, whose form appears to be both natural and highly effective. For further details on this type of issues, see [14, 13]. In particular, generalized fractional integrals play a crucial role in developing inequalities, where one of the most important applications is the Hermite–Hadamard inequality and its various extensions. For instance, In [15], Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities for fractional integrals are first established. Then, an integral identity and several Hermite–Hadamard-type integral inequalities for fractional integrals are obtained, which are related to the results in [16]. In [16], the authors offer two inequalities for differentiable convex mappings which are connected with the celebrated Hermite–Hadamard-type integral inequality holding for convex functions. For further information and unexplained subjects about these type of inequalities, we refer the reader to [17, 18, 19] and the references therein.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, several definitions and notations frequently used throughout the main part of the paper are introduced. Simpson’s quadrature formula (Simpson’s 1/3 rule) is presented as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

Theorem 2.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Simpson’s second formula, also known as the Newton-Cotes quadrature formula (Simpson’s 3/8 rule; see [20]), is expressed as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Theorem 2.2. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

The corresponding dual Simpson’s 3/8 formula - the Maclaurin rule based on the Maclaurin formula (cf. [20]) is as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

Theorem 2.3. Suppose that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function

on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7}{51840} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Formulae (1), (2), and (3) hold for every function f with continuous 4th derivative on $[a, b]$.

In the literature, numerous studies address inequalities related to generalized fractional integrals. For instance, Sarikaya and Ertugral [17] have established Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities for generalized fractional integrals.

Definition 2.1. [17] Let us consider $\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ the condition $\int_0^1 \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} dt < \infty$. Then, the following left-sided and right-sided generalized fractional integral operators are described as

$${}_{a+}I_\varphi f(x) = \int_a^x \frac{\varphi(x-t)}{x-t} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \tag{4}$$

and

$${}_{b-}I_\varphi f(x) = \int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t-x)}{t-x} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \tag{5}$$

respectively.

Generalized fractional integrals possess the notable feature of encompassing several important types of fractional integrals, including the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, Katugampola fractional integrals, conformable fractional integral, and Hadamard fractional integrals, among others. The key special cases of the integral operators defined in (4) and (5) are summarized as follows:

- i. If we choose $\varphi(t) = t$, then the operators (4) and (5) reduce to the Riemann integral.
- ii. If we select $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ and $\alpha > 0$, then the operators (4) and (5) become to the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively [21, 22]. Here,

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ is Gamma function defined by the integral formula

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

- iii. For $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ and $\alpha, k > 0$, the operators (4) and (5) equal to the k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively. Here,

$$J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ_k is k -Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{t^k}{k}} dt, \quad \Re(\alpha) > 0$$

and

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = k^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{k}\right), \quad \Re(\alpha) > 0; k > 0.$$

3 Main results

Lemma 3.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_\varphi f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + {}_{a+}I_\varphi f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ & = \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b K(x) df(x). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here, $\Lambda(t) = \int_0^t \frac{\varphi\left(\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)y\right)}{y} dy$ and

$$K(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{2}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right], & a \leq x < \frac{2a+b}{3}, \\ -\frac{2}{b-a} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right), & \frac{2a+b}{3} \leq x < \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \frac{2}{b-a} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right), & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x < \frac{a+2b}{3}, \\ \frac{2}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{a+2b}{3} \leq x \leq b. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let us first consider the function $K(x)$. Then, with the help of the integrating by parts, it follows from that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b K(x) df(x) \\ & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ - \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right) df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) df(x) \\
 & + \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \Bigg\} \\
 & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ - \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right) \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} - \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} \frac{\varphi \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)}{\frac{a+b}{2} - x} f(x) dx \right. \\
 & - \Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right) \right) f(x) \Big|_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} - \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \frac{\varphi \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)}{\frac{a+b}{2} - x} f(x) dx \\
 & + \Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \frac{\varphi \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)}{x - \frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) dx \\
 & \left. + \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b - \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \frac{\varphi \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)}{x - \frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) dx \right\} \\
 & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{\Lambda(1)}{4} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \frac{\varphi \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)}{\frac{a+b}{2} - x} f(x) dx - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \frac{\varphi \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)}{x - \frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) dx \right\} \\
 & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{\Lambda(1)}{4} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. - \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \\
 & = \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b K(x) df(x).
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.1. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then it follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1), \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f).
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\bigvee_a^b(f)$ denotes the total variation of f on $[a, b]$.

Proof. It is well-known that if $g, f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with g continuous on $[a, b]$ and f of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then the integral $\int_a^b g(t) df(t)$ exists and

$$\left| \int_a^b g(t) df(t) \right| \leq \sup_{t \in [a, b]} |g(t)| \bigvee_a^b(f). \quad (8)$$

With the aid of (8), it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ &= \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \left| \int_a^b K_{\alpha}(x) df(x) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \left| \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \right. \\ &\quad + \left| \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) df(x) \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) df(x) \right| \\ &\quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{2a+b}{3}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}}(f) \right. \\ &\quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{2a+b}{3}, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\ &\quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+2b}{3}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}}(f) \\ &\quad \left. + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+2b}{3}, b]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b(f) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \max \left[\left| \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] \bigvee_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}}(f) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \bigvee_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}}(f) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1) \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b (f) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1), \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) \right\} \bigvee_a^b (f).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 3.1. □

Remark 3.1. Consider $\varphi(t) = t$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, the following Newton-type inequality satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{5}{24} \bigvee_a^b (f).$$

This is presented by which is given by Alomari in [24].

Remark 3.2. Consider $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, Theorem 3.1 is equal to [23, Theorem 3.17].

Corollary 3.1. Note that $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, it follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{2^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{(b-a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}} \left[J_{b^-,k}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{a^+,k}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ \left| \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} - \frac{3}{4} \right|, \frac{1}{4}, \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \right\} \bigvee_a^b (f).
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Concluding Remarks and Summary

We prove Newton-type inequalities using generalized fractional integrals of bounded variation, and the results are demonstrated through special cases of the established theories. In future studies, the concepts and techniques underlying our results on Newton-type inequalities using generalized fractional integrals could pave the way for further research in this area. Enhancements or generalizations of our findings may be explored by examining different classes of convex functions or alternative types of fractional integral operators. Furthermore, Newton-type inequalities for various function classes might be derived with the assistance of quantum calculus.

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